

Secure Information Exchange between Optical Network Digital Twin and Optical Transport Network

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Abstract— This paper explores the role of data spaces in enabling secure, interoperable data exchange between Network Digital Twins and SDN Controllers. This approach emphasizes data space connectors for faster, scalable, and flexible integration of multiple components across digital ecosystems to work in unison. The proposed approach is to use a common trusted platform (in this paper, the platform used is TRUE Connector) which is responsible for secure information exchange between components (e.g: SDN Controller, Network Digital Twins, Software applications, etc.) in a digital ecosystem, thus encouraging collaboration between multiple technology vendors to provide more efficient network services and encourage interoperability.

Index Terms—International Data Space - TRUE Connector, ADRENALINE Testbed, Interoperability.

I. INTRODUCTION

An optical network digital twin is a virtual representation of an optical communication network, designed to accurately model its physical counterpart in a digital environment. This digital twin replicates the infrastructure, components, and operational conditions of the optical network, including fiber links, optical amplifiers, routers, and switching elements. It is built using real-time data, analytics, and artificial intelligence to ensure a precise and dynamic simulation. Unlike a simple network simulation, which may be static and hypothetical, a digital twin continuously synchronizes with the physical network, reflecting changes and variations in performance. The model integrates multiple layers of the network architecture, capturing not only the physical topology but also logical connections and traffic patterns. It leverages historical and real-time data to provide an evolving and contextually accurate digital counterpart of the optical network using advanced modeling, data analytics and sometimes coupled with AI applications for further enhanced, automated network optimization.

A digital twin provides network operators with valuable insights into network behavior, this can be used as input to develop solutions to mitigate potential failures, and develop network optimization strategies dynamically and in an automated fashion. This technology is crucial in improving network

efficiency, enhancing resilience, and supporting proactive maintenance by predicting faults before they occur [1]. Additionally, it facilitates the integration of emerging technologies such as 5G and edge computing by providing a risk-free environment for experimentation and innovation. By incorporating digital twins, organizations can achieve cost savings, improve decision-making, and enhance overall network performance in an increasingly complex digital landscape.[2]. Thus, the importance of NDT can be seen.

Optical networks, known for their high-speed data transmission capabilities through fiber optic cables which are used extensively in telecommunications network architectures, require effective coordination and real-time data sharing between various network elements such as optical switches, routers, ROADMs, optical amplifiers, network controllers, etc. and their virtual counterpart in the optical network digital twin. The real-time data nature of optical networks requires a framework for data sharing that maintains control over data sovereignty, enabling organizations to share valuable information without losing ownership or compromising security. As mentioned in the abstract, the platform used for secure data exchange is called an International Data Space (IDS). IDS represents a conceptual framework for secure information exchange between multiple stakeholders within a network infrastructure [3]. IDSs provide a structured environment where data can be shared and managed according to agreed-upon governance rules, ensuring interoperability, security, and privacy. Data spaces have been demonstrated as a feasible solution that enables the sharing of monitored and telemetry data securely and efficiently, allowing improved network management, service orchestration, and more accurate network monitoring.[4]

This paper presents a recent innovation in ETSI Ter-aFlowSDN (TFS) Software Defined Networking (SDN) Controller, namely the introduction of the IDS Gateway, which enhances the speed and security of data exchange. At the core of the IDS Gateway architecture lies the IDS Connector, which acts as the gateway between existing systems and the

IDS ecosystem. This connector enables secure data exchange enriched with metadata. It is built on the principles defined by the IDS Reference Architecture Model [3].

This paper presents an architecture for the deployment of an optical NDT from the optical SDN controller and its integration with the IDS framework to evaluate the feasibility of the presented solution. The structure of this paper is as follows. Section II contains related work which highlights the importance of IDS and NDTs. Section III contains the architecture that is introduced in this paper for secure information exchange between the NDT and the actual optical network. Section IV contains the experimental validation of the architecture discussed in III and the factors affecting the observed results, finally the V ends the paper highlighting the value of this paper.

II. RELATED WORK

This section shall analyze previous work done in the area of International Data Spaces and Network Digital Twins focusing, specifically in optical network digital twins in Network Infrastructure and digital ecosystems focusing on the role it plays in communication between networks and the digital twins of networks. The paper by authors Kalogeropoulous et al. introduces the concept Edge Data Space (EdgeDS) which is a novel approach in integrating IDS with Multi-Access Edge Compute (MEC) to enable diverse stakeholders within the MEC and out of the MEC to communicate with each other in a safe and secured fashion. The paper talks about IDS-as-a-Service where IDS Connectors are instantiated as needed to offer connectivity between MEC applications and applications in the MEC and cloud of the Telco-cloud infrastructure. It also discusses the life-cycle management of IDS connectors from composing, instantiating, deploying and managing IDS Connectors and MEC Applications.[2]. The paper discusses how this could be leveraged by autonomous driving systems for faster, efficient transportation. In the paper by Nast et al. the authors discuss about the potential of using IDS Connectors in the area of Internet-of-Things (IoT), the paper highlights that almost half of the devices connected to the internet are IoT devices and the vast amount of data generated must be secured at transit and at rest. An IDS Connector is used to connect cloud environments to IoT devices. The IDS Connectors are designed to be gatekeepers between information stored in internal infrastructure and the data space. The IDS architecture uses CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) principles of Representational State Transfer (REST) Application Programming Interface (API) to foster communication between multiple stakeholders like IoT client Devices, applications running in the cloud, data stream brokers (e.g. Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT)) to name a few. The paper discusses the architecture to collect, integrate and send sensor data from IoT devices to the cloud environments (data at transit) that process the data in a secure way using IDS Connectors and vice-versa. Data sharing is done as data objects using JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) back and forth entities via an IDS Connector [5]. From the book written by authors Otto et al. [6] in chapter

17, the authors talk about the use of IDS in the digitalization of the agricultural ecosystem. The importance of creation of an IoT enabled ecosystem for precision based farming and automated management of watering of crops based on need, monitoring of individual crops in agricultural field is discussed. Upon creation of a digital ecosystem of agriculture, the need for a secure information exchange between IoT devices, edge/cloud servers, software applications is stated, this technical gap can be solved by the use of IDS space, a new nomenclature is defined, where the use of an IDS in the agricultural ecosystem is called as 'Agricultural Data Space' (ADS). These are some potential applications which highlight the importance of IDS in different industries including networking and telecommunications.

The paper by Zalat et al. discusses on the use of network digital twins of a transport network. A Transport network is designed to transport IP packets from source to destination (which are spatially separated) as fast as possible, the authors discuss using the interior gateway protocol called Open Shortest Path First (OSPF) protocol to route packets from source to destination servers. The concept of using a Graph Neural Network (GNN) as a network twin is introduced to optimize parameters used in the OSPF's Dijkstra's algorithm to find most optimal routes from source to destination within a network. Different algorithms are used on the network digital twin to find the optimal path to route the packets within the network and the performance of each algorithm can be compared to choose the best parameters of the Dijkstra's algorithm of the OSPF protocol. Thus, this method proactive optimization ensures network efficiency at all times, and any changes made in the network twin does not affect the actual physical network [7]. NDTs also are an inevitable component in the design and development of autonomous networking systems in a network infrastructure, as is shown in the paper by [8] it shows the use of NDTs playing a crucial part in autonomous networking, the paper discusses the Autonomous Trusted Network (ATN) framework which makes use of NDTs and takes it a step further by also incorporating Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), and large language models (LLMs) to enhance cybersecurity through proactive attack prevention unlike traditional reactive methods which are deployed after the damage to a network has been done, ATN predicts security threats in real-time using intelligent configuration policies and flexible data aggregation techniques. By integrating software-defined networking and real-time telemetry to the network digital twin ensuring automated, AI-driven security management. The authors of the paper [8] perform an experimental validation of the ATN's effectiveness against Link-Flooding Attacks (LFA) in mitigating attacks while maintaining legitimate traffic flow, outperforming conventional filtering and rerouting techniques. Predictive maintenance is performed on the NDT before being implemented on the actual network, collected real-time traffic is fed into the NDT, the authors use the software tool OMNET++ to simulate a network, where a GNN is used to determine if network traffic is benign or malicious when malicious network traffic is detected, appropriate Access Control List (ACLs)

are incorporated in the NDT and verified if it mitigates the malicious traffic in the NDT. Thus, the importance of NDT in cybersecurity is clearly demonstrated. The paper by authors Vilata et al. [1] demonstrate the use of NDT of an optical transport network. The authors explore the possibility of using optical transport network's NDT to improve network optimization, decision making and testing. The paper also describes the integration of cloud and a distributed network architecture where the real physical optical transport network is on premise while the SDN controller which is the ETSI TeraflowSDN (TFS) is located in the cloud along with the NDT of the optical transport network. The NDT is created by instantiating a topology of the optical network in mininet optical. The cloud environment also included the Network Function Virtualization - Orchestrator (NFV-O) which is accessible to TFS and the NDT. The paper demonstrates the experimental validation of setting up a service which requires the instantiation of an NDT performed by the NFV-O and life-cycle management of the NDT including operations like automated continual updation of physical network in real-time using Kafka messaging [9] bus as a data-stream with all necessary information which is fed to the NDT from the real physical network to accurately replicate the real physical optical transport network. This paper proves the potential NDTs of optical networks have in automated network operations.

III. ARCHITECTURE

The architecture of the experimental setup this paper proposes is shown in the Fig. 1, it provides an architectural design for the integration of a NDT (here: an Optical NDT) with the SDN infrastructure that spans the entire optical domain. At the top, the IDS-Connector serves as a key component, linking the deployed NDT and the measurements received by TFS. The IDS-Connector plays a critical role in facilitating seamless and secure data exchanges between the various systems involved, ensuring interoperability and real-time communication. The NDT which is positioned at the top-right, showcases the virtual representation of the physical network. Within this module, an SDN Controller is responsible for orchestrating and simulating various network components such as ROADMs (Reconfigurable Optical Add-Drop Multiplexers), optical transponders, TX/RX (transmit/receive) units. The dashed lines between these virtual components indicate how the NDT reflects the relationships and inter-dependencies in the real network. This digital twin provides a real-time, dynamic model of the physical network, allowing for simulation, monitoring, and predictive analytics, all controlled by the SDN controller which controls the NDT. An instance of the TFS controller acts as the optical SDN framework, it manages the optical network layer, depicted in the lower left section of the image. This layer includes fiber optic components, such as optical transponders and ROADMs, which are used to route and manage wavelengths across the optical fiber links. Thus, this architecture can be summarized as a physical optical network which is connected to an instance of the TFS SDN controller where the SDN controller is connected

to the IDS-Connector and the IDS-Connector is connected to the TFS instance which manages the optical NDT. Thus ensuring any communication back and forth the optical network and the optical NDT is possible only via the IDS-Connector and the IDS-Connector guarantees safe exchange of information between entities, the entities here being the optical network and the optical NDT. The sequence diagram (Fig. 1 (right)) illustrates the interactions among various components within a network management system orchestrated by a Network Operator. The system components include the TeraFlowSDN (comprising the main involved components: Optical SDN controller, NDT manager, and IDS Gateway), the Data Space Connector (DSC) which is the IDS-Connector instance, and the NDT. The diagram is organized into three main phases: NDT Initialization, Runtime Operations, and What-if Operation.

- **NDT Initialization:** the Network Operator requests the setup of the NDT. The NDT Manager deploys the Data Space Connector (DSC) through the IDS Gateway, sets up the NDT, and configures the digital twin environment. The NDT communicates with the DSC to establish data exchange mechanisms. Once the setup is complete, the IDS Gateway notifies the Network Operator.
- **Runtime Operations:** In the Runtime Operations phase, real-time network data flows through the system for monitoring, analysis, and decision-making purposes. The Optical SDN controller receives real-time network data that is forwarded to the IDS Gateway, which acts as an intermediary to ensure secure and efficient data transfer. IDS Gateway then transmits the data to the DSC, which is responsible for facilitating data exchange between different system components. The DSC relays the real-time network data to the NDT, where the data is used to update the digital representation of the network. This continuous data flow ensures that the NDT accurately reflects the current state of the physical network, enabling real-time monitoring and analysis.
- **What-if Operations:** During the What-if Operation phase, the Network Administrator requests a scenario analysis from the NDT. That is, the NDT recreates particular conditions or changes within the network which is aimed at predicting potential outcomes without affecting the live network. The NDT processes this request internally, running the scenario based on its current state and the parameters provided by the operator. After completing the simulation, the NDT returns the results to the Network Operator.

The integration of NDT with IDS-Connector increases better automated network operations optimization, secure data exchange, and enables interoperability between different systems.

IV. EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

We have evaluated in the ADRENALINE Testbed, the communication between the IDS Gateway and the NDT (using mininet-optical[8]), which contains a virtual replica of the testbed. The code has not been optimized for speed. To

Fig. 1. NDT for Network Operations.

communicate between the ADRENALINE Testbed and the NDT, TRUE Connector is selected as the IDS Connector. True Connector is an open-source DSC developed by Engineering (ENG) organization. In this experiment the security mechanism used for inter-communication between IDS Gateway and NDT is Basic Authorization which is Hyper-Text Transfer Protocol (HTTP) enabled, TRUE Connector also provides more advanced security mechanisms, such as Transport Layer Security (TLS) using Secured Hash Algorithm (SHA) 256 and by issuing a trust certificate to each entity connected to the DSC, thus ensuring further enhanced secure communication between entities in the Data Space. In this experimental setup, a connectivity service is posted into the NDT to replicate a configuration of the real optical network. IDS Gateway posts the connectivity service as a json object into the DSC and an automated POST request notification is sent to the REST server that is built-in the NDT which contains the unique identifier of the object posted into DSC. Once the POST notification action is complete, the NDT which now has the unique identifier of the JSON object present in the DSC, it performs a GET request to the DSC to retrieve the JSON object (i.e. connectivity service) from the DSC. The DSC verifies the credentials of both entities based on username and password which are sent as payload in the GET request made by the NDT to the DSC instance. Upon successful authentication it serves the object to the NDT which is pushed as a connection in the mininet-optical. The entire process from TFS controller posting the connectivity service into the DSC instance and the NDT obtaining the connectivity service from the DSC instance and implementing it in the NDT is completely automated without any human intervention. The optical network topology as can be seen in Fig. 1 consists of four switches where each switch is connected to an optical network terminal and the optical network terminal is connected to a Reconfigurable Optical Add/Drop Multiplexer (ROADM), these four ROADMs are in turn connected to each other.

The Fig. 2 shows the Cumulative Distributive Function (CDF) graph of the time taken to instantiate the optical-mininet NDT which replicates the ADRENALINE Testbed present in

CTTC. The NDT is instantiated and all elements in the NDT are configured to mimic connectivity between elements of the actual ADRENALINE Testbed. The NDT was instantiated over 50 times and the time taken to instantiate and configure the optical network topology is recorded for each instance and the CDF is plotted. It can be seen from Fig. 2 that 80 percent of the NDT instantiations occur in a duration of 10.8 seconds with a maximum time of 15.66 seconds to instantiate the NDT. The mean time to instantiate the NDT is 10.43 seconds and the median time to instantiate the NDT is 9.99 seconds.

Fig. 2. Time taken to instantiate transport network twin on mininet-optical

The Fig. 3 represents the time to POST a connectivity service as a JSON object from the TFS instance of the actual network into the DSC instance. From the Fig. 3 which is a CDF plot of the cumulative time taken to POST the JSON object in the DSC, it can be seen that the 80 percent of the time taken to POST into DSC in 0.53 seconds. The mean time taken to POST an object into the DSC is 0.48 seconds and the median time taken is 0.44 seconds.

Finally, the Fig. 4 shows the CDF distribution of the time taken to perform a GET request by the NDT to the DSC and

Fig. 3. Time taken to POST connectivity service to DSC

obtain the JSON object (connectivity service) posted in the DSC by the TFS controller of the actual network. From Fig. 4 it can be seen that the 80% of the time take to GET the object resource from the DSC takes 0.45 seconds, the mean time to retrieve the JSON object from the DSC Connector is 0.39 seconds with a median time of 0.38 s. The maximum time observed to retrieve an object in the validation is 0.68 s.

Fig. 4. Time taken to GET connectivity service from DSC

The performance and effectiveness of the proposed approach might be evaluated based on data exchange latency, which refers to the time taken to POST and GET resources via the DSC, which affects the responsiveness of the NDT. The factors that affect NDT initialization time are attributed to control plane overhead, computational resources available on the node of NDT instantiation. The latency in time taken to POST and GET resources to and from the DSC Connector can be attributed to factors like bandwidth available at Transport Net-

work, the communication overhead due to size of data payload (connectivity service JSON object) that is sent in IP packets, the security overhead due to encryption mechanisms. Possible next steps would be to validate it against real-time mitigation of cyber-security attacks on the physical network using a NDT, where the physical network and NDT are physically separated and connected together via the data space.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper shows the novel architecture design which enhances secure information exchange of connectivity services between the actual physical optical network and the Network Digital Twin of the optical network, this design helps in better replication and higher fidelity in real-time of the NDT with respect to the actual physical optical network.

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REFERENCES

- [1] R. Vilalta, L. Gifre, R. Casellas, R. Muñoz, R. Martínez, A. Mozo, A. Pastor, D. López, and J. P. Fernández-Palacios, "Applying digital twins to optical networks with cloud-native sdn controllers," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 61, no. 12, pp. 128–134, 2023.
- [2] I. Kalogeropoulos, M. E. Vrontzou, N. Psaromanolakis, E. Zarogianni, and V. Theodorou, "Edgeds: Data spaces enabled multi-access edge computing," in *2023 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 424–429.
- [3] B. Otto, S. Lohmann, S. Steinbuss, A. Teuscher, S. Auer, M. Boehmer, J. Bohn, G. Brost, J. Cirullies, C. Ciureanu *et al.*, "Ids reference architecture model. industrial data space. version 2.0," 2018.
- [4] B. Shariat, H. Qarawlus, S. Biehs, J.-J. Pedreno-Manresa, P. Safari, M. Balanici, A. Bouchedoub, H. Haße, A. Autenrieth, J. K. Fischer *et al.*, "Telemetry framework with data sovereignty features," in *Optical Fiber Communication Conference*. Optica Publishing Group, 2023, pp. M3G–2.
- [5] M. Nast, B. Rother, F. Golasowski, D. Timmermann, J. Leveling, C. Olms, and C. Nissen, "Work-in-progress: Towards an international data spaces connector for the internet of things," in *2020 16th IEEE International Conference on Factory Communication Systems (WFCS)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 1–4.
- [6] B. Otto, M. Hompel, and S. Wrobel, *Designing Data Spaces*, 07 2022.
- [7] M. Zalat, C. Barber, D. Krauss, B. Esfandiari, and T. Kunz, "Network routing optimization using digital twins," in *PoEM Companion*, 2023.
- [8] Y. Liu, W. Zhang, L. Li, J. Wu, Y. Xia, S. Gao, and H. Zhang, "Toward autonomous trusted networks-from digital twin perspective," *IEEE Network*, 2024.
- [9] J. Kreps, N. Narkhede, J. Rao *et al.*, "Kafka: A distributed messaging system for log processing," in *Proceedings of the NetDB*, vol. 11, no. 2011. Athens, Greece, 2011, pp. 1–7.